

Development and Implementation of a Model Architecture for the Preliminary Design of a Ground Segment in CDP4-COMET

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Abstract. This paper presents a model architecture for preliminary Ground Segment and Operations (GS&OPS) design using CDP4-COMET. Emphasizing the synergy between Concurrent Engineering (CE) and Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE), the model aims to bridge traditional CE methodologies and the unique challenges of GS&OPS. Real-world data validation demonstrates the model's suitability for GS&OPS planning, showcasing its practical applicability for modern space missions within the MBSE framework.

Keywords: Concurrent Engineering · Ground Segment and Operations

1 Introduction and Background

The evolution of space missions demands a paradigm shift in mission design methodologies. While Concurrent Engineering (CE) traditionally focused on space systems conceptual design, ground segments and utilization aspects were typically considered only at a higher level, and favoring conventional approaches and designs. The increasing complexity of space missions, driven by satellite constellations and user demands, necessitates a more flexible framework. As space missions evolve, there is a move away from the traditional top-down approach to mission planning. Instead, missions are now being initiated from a GS&OPS perspective, with users actively involved in defining mission conditions and requirements. This user-centered approach highlights the limitations of relying solely on established solutions without thorough technical considerations. It emphasizes the importance of moving beyond familiar solutions without proactive engineering. This transformation requires an innovative and user-centric approach to manage the operational complexity of larger constellations and integrated applications. In response to the challenges faced in modern space missions, the Technical University of Darmstadt (TU Darmstadt) and the European Space Agency (ESA) joined forces to create the Concurrent Engineering Lab (CEL). The CEL focuses on developing innovative solutions for complex technical systems, integrating CE principles with MBSE methodologies. Positioned at the intersection of CE and GS&OPS design, the CEL aims to advance space engineering through collaborative efforts.

This paper presents the development and implementation of a model architecture tailored specifically for the preliminary design of GS&OPS within CDP4-COMET (COMET), ESA’s chosen CE server software. The motivation behind this endeavour lies in bridging the gap between traditional CE methodologies, primarily designed for space segments, and the unique challenges posed by the ground segment.

ESOC is transitioning towards a MBSE paradigm for GS&OPS engineering. The development of the “Ground Segment Engineering Framework” (GSEF) [1] supports digital continuity across lifecycle phases. The activity DGSO-A [1] enhances GSEF to cover operations engineering concerns, such as mission operations concept definition and COMET product trees. This motivates the model architecture’s development: previously, few parameters were generated during CE studies for GS&OPS. The model digitises and formalises this GS&OPS artefact, allowing exchange between MBSE tools, improving efficiency, and enabling formal traceability to mission-specific implementations and extensions.

This paper aims to contribute to this overarching goal. Through a comprehensive validation and testing process, leveraging real-world data from ESA missions, the paper demonstrates the suitability of the model architecture for preliminary GS&OPS design. The integration within COMET showcases its practical applicability, offering a valuable resource for mission planners and engineers dealing with the complexities of the modern space engineering landscape.

2 Model Architecture for a Ground Segment

2.1 Development Process of the Model Architecture

The model architecture was required to meet two criteria during development: it should be generally applicable to all potential missions, while also being customisable to specific missions, ensuring it can serve as a foundation for planning future missions.

The development involved an analysis and adaptation of existing architectures from successful ESA missions, such as Integral [2], non-ESA missions such as Radarsat-2 [3], the ECSS-E-ST-70C standard [4], the CubeSat System Reference Model (CSRM) from the Space System Working Group at INCOSE [5], relevant literature in space mission engineering [6] and expert interviews at ESOC in the fields of GS&OPS and MBSE.

2.2 Structure of the Model Architecture

The developed model architecture, shown in Figure 1, is subdivided into four main components: Mission Operations Centre, Ground Station Centre, Payload Operations & Data Centre, and Ground Communications System. This classification is in accordance with the ECSS-E-ST-70C standard [4]. Each component is further subdivided into subsystems, providing more detailed representation than in the ECSS-E-ST-70C standard.

Fig. 1. Developed model architecture in a Capella Logical Architecture Diagram.

2.3 Implementation of the Model Architecture in COMET

The developed model architecture has been implemented in the CE server software COMET. The implementation uses the template model as the model type, ensuring the requirements of generality and customisability. In a CE study, the template model can be selected and adapted to the mission's requirements.

After creating the template model in COMET, the next step is to define the Domains of Expertise (DoEs) of the model. The standard directory implemented in COMET provides the users with a variety of possible DoEs. However, these existing DoEs are primarily designed for the preliminary design of the space segment of a mission and are not suitable for the detailed representation of a ground segment. Therefore, additional DoEs were created to address this issue: Communications, Flight Dynamics, Ground Segment Systems and Operations.

The model architecture's various systems and subsystems were created using COMET's system and subsystem categories. To contextualize them, a superordinate Ground Segment was also created. The Launch Segment and Space Segment were added and assigned to a Mission to represent the mission completely. However, these two segments were not further populated as the focus is on the Ground Segment. The resulting product tree's structure is depicted in Figure 2.

In addition to the systems and subsystems depicted in Figure 1, a Generic Ground Segment Centre and its associated Generic Ground Segment Subsystem

Fig. 2. COMET product tree of the developed model architecture with some exemplary parameters.

have been implemented in COMET. This allows, in certain cases, special systems to be easily included in the model if required by the mission, thus enhancing the customizability, which is a key requirement.

The system-level parameters added to the architecture are of a general nature and describe aspects such as the physical size of the system, the cost of operating the system, the location, and the mission specificity, i.e. whether the system is dedicated to the planned mission or shared with other missions.

At the subsystem level, parameters were added mainly relating to personnel and associated costs. However, additional parameters were assigned to certain subsystems. For instance, the Wide Area Network Subsystem has been assigned several network parameters, including data rate, data volume, and the underlying protocol. The Ground Data Handling Subsystem was assigned parameters describing the level of data processing and the storage capacity of the archive.

The antenna, a component of the Space-Ground Communications Subsystem, was assigned by far the largest number of parameters, including location, diameter, speed of elevation or azimuth movement. Additionally, the antenna was divided into three components: baseband, receiver, and transmitter. Specific parameters were assigned, including the data rate, frequency band, and modulation or demodulation scheme used.

2.4 Validation of the Implemented Model Architecture

The validation of the model architecture developed and implemented in COMET is a multi-stage and iterative process. The initial stage of validation has already been completed, using the Mission Operations Assumptions Document (MOAD) and the Space to Ground Interface Control Document (SG-ICD) produced at the end of Phase A of the ground segment life cycle of several real ESA missions. The missions under review are the EnVision mission, the Mars Sample Return-Earth Return Orbiter mission, and the Euclid mission.

All parameters required for a CE study were collected from the respective MOADs and SG-ICDs. The data was entered into new COMET models, based on the template model. The ESTRACK Facilities Manual (EFM) was used to complete the data. This allowed for the addition of a number of elements and parameters to the COMET models. It was noted that some SG-ICD link budget parameters were absent from the EFM, which was used as a reference for creating the parameters in the template model. Thus, these parameters were added to both the mission study models and the template model.

The use of finite states in COMET proved to be very beneficial. It allows for the linking of mission phases and satellite states, allowing the dependency of parameters on these, leading to a more accurate cost estimate.

Certain parameters, though, remained unspecified in the MOADs or SG-ICDs, or were not listed at all, preventing their transfer to the COMET model. Out of the 17 subsystems depicted in Figure 1, five were not parameterised or the parameters provided in the template model for these subsystems could not be populated based on the documents used. This applies to the Communications Management Subsystem, the Payload Data Distribution Subsystem and all three Facilities Subsystems. To ensure the meaningfulness of the implementation of these subsystems further validation is required.

In order to provide further validation, a series of expert interviews were conducted with individuals specialising in the fields of CE, MBSE, COMET, and Cost Engineering. The experts were provided with the developed GS&OPS template model in advance, allowing them to analyse it at their own pace. Feedback was subsequently obtained through free individual and group interviews. The experts interviewed stated that the model architecture developed was comprehensive and well implemented in COMET. However, it was also emphasised that only parameters that are actually needed for the respective study should be added to the COMET model so that the model remains practical. The number of these useful parameters differs from study to study.

Nevertheless, during the validation process, it has not yet been possible to conduct a real CE study with the developed model architecture. Consequently, conducting a study utilising a fictitious test case or even a real mission would represent the subsequent step in the validation process, paving the way for the full utilisation of CE with the developed model architecture in the development of new ground segments. However, the validation thus far can be considered successful. The MOAD and SG-ICD parameters of the different analysed missions could be seamlessly integrated into COMET, and the developed model architec-

ture was positively evaluated by experts. This illustrates the value of the model for GS&OPS planning.

3 Conclusion and Next Steps

The presented model architecture serves as a fundamental framework for designing ground segments for various missions, highlighting the critical role of ground segment engineering in mission conceptual design. This research, addressing the intricacies of ground segment design within COMET, contributes valuable insights to the broader field of MBSE in space systems. By optimising MBSE applications for space mission design, the study underscores potential advancements for downstream applications and collaborative efforts in ground segment engineering, aligning seamlessly with the evolving landscape of space systems engineering.

Moving forward, contact has been established with the ESTEC CDF team, and the COMET template of the system model has been provided. Utilising this template in real-world CDF studies, particularly focusing on GS&OPS, such as Galileo missions or activities in the Space Safety sector, will be advantageous. Subsequently, validating the comprehensiveness and benefits of the template for the CE process is crucial.

Furthermore, analysing the value of data generated from these studies for the general digital project lifecycle would be beneficial, supporting the overarching goal of the GSEF initiative. The subsequent tracking and validation of the COMET product tree data within this activity will be essential for enhancing interoperability and streamlining design processes within the space engineering community.

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